

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ALUMINUM BORATE WHISKER REINFORCED
ALUMINUM ALLOYS AND INTERFACE STRUCTURE

K.Suganuma, G.Sasaki, T.Fujita,
Department of Materials Science and Technology,
National Defense Academy, Yokosuka, Kanagawa 239, Japan

and N.Suzuki
Advanced Materials Technology, Matsunaga 622-1,
Numazu, Shizuoka 410, Japan

ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties and microstructures of the aluminum alloys reinforced with the new aluminum borate whisker fabricated by the squeeze casting has been examined. Comparison of the mechanical properties of the 6061 alloy matrix composites with various whiskers, i.e. silicon carbide, silicon nitride and potassium titanate whiskers, made the advantage of the new whisker clearer. The strength and Young's modulus of the composite with aluminum borate whiskers were comparable to those with silicon carbide whiskers or with silicon nitride whiskers. The thermal expansion coefficient was low as that with silicon nitride whiskers. The AC8A alloy matrix composite with randomly oriented 20 vol% aluminum borate whiskers maintained the strength of 250 MPa up to 300°C, which strength is comparable with that with silicon carbide whisker. Slight reaction between the whisker and aluminum alloys was observed by using transmission electron microscopy. The reaction product was primarily fine $MgAl_2O_3$ (or γ -alumina) precipitates formed on a whisker. Those precipitates had a good epitaxial relationship with the whisker and seems to adhere to the whisker tightly. The aluminum borate whisker is expected to be one of the promising whisker reinforcing aluminum alloys because of its excellent ability in reinforcing aluminum alloys in addition to the low cost.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Whisker; Aluminum borate whisker; Aluminum alloy; Transmission electron microscopy; Strength; Young's modulus.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many kinds of ceramic whiskers have been developed and have been examined as a reinforcing element of aluminum alloys. Silicon carbide whisker is one of promising whiskers for aluminum matrix composites because of its high strength, high modulus and low thermal expansion characteristics. However, the high cost of the silicon carbide whisker sometimes prevents the wide commercial applications such as automobile engine components. Potassium titanate whisker and alumina short fiber can be applicable to such low-cost products and, in fact, alumina-silica fiber has been used for reinforcing a piston of an automobile engine in commercial scale(1). However, they cannot supply the same level in mechanical properties to silicon carbide whisker.

Aluminum borate whisker ($9\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$), which has been commercially available since 1989, has good mechanical properties, i.e. high strength and modulus, and is cheap as potassium titanate whisker. This whisker, therefore, has a potential as the reinforcing whisker for aluminum alloys. The authors have briefly reported some properties of the aluminum matrix composite with this whisker(2). The aim of the present paper was to show the details of the mechanical properties of the aluminum matrix composites with aluminum borate whiskers and the interface microstructure in the composite observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and Casting Aluminum borate whisker was supplied from Shikoku Chemicals Co. (Marugame, Japan). The diameter and length of the whiskers are 0.5-1.0 μm and 10-30 μm , respectively. In order to compare the reinforcing ability against aluminum alloys, β -phase silicon carbide whisker, α -phase silicon nitride whisker, and potassium titanate whisker and alumina-silica short fiber were also used to fabricate composites. Aluminum alloys used as the matrix were 6061 alloy and AC8A alloy (Al-12wt%Si). Composites were fabricated by the conventional squeeze casting method. The whiskers and fiber were sintered to be preforms with a small amount of silica as binder to be 20 vol% of whiskers in a composite. The temperature of the alloy melts and the preforms were 800°C and that of the mold was 250°C. The casting was carried out in air atmosphere under a pressure of 100 MPa.

2.2 Mechanical Properties Tensile strength was evaluated up to 300°C at maximum. The cross section of the tensile specimen was 1.5 mm x 4 mm

rectangular and the gage length was 10 mm. The strain rate was 1.0×10^{-4} /s. Young's modulus at room temperature and average thermal expansion coefficient between room temperature and 300°C were also measured on each composite. All specimen were heat-treated before testing in the T6 condition.

2.3 Microstructure Microstructure of the aluminum borate whisker reinforced composite was examined mainly by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). TEM specimen was prepared by combining the conventional electrolytic polishing and ion thinning. The microscope used was JEOL JEM200CX operated at 200 kV. X-ray diffraction measurement on the extracted whisker from the composite was also performed to identify reaction products.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Comparison of Properties Figure 1 shows the summary of tensile strength, Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient of 6061 alloys reinforced with various whiskers and with alumina-silica fiber. Aluminum borate whisker gives the composite both high strength and high Young's modulus, which are almost comparable to those values of the composites with silicon carbide whiskers or with silicon nitride whiskers. The thermal expansion coefficient of the composite with aluminum borate whiskers is also as low as those high quality composites. On the contrary, the composites reinforced with potassium titanate whiskers or with alumina-silica fibers showed a slight lower strength, lower Young's modulus and larger thermal expansion but those values are better than those of 6061 alloy.

Table 2 summarize mechanical and thermal properties of the aluminum borate whisker reinforced AC8A alloy. Strength, Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient are almost the same as those of the 6061 matrix composite. Figure 2 shows temperature dependence of tensile strength of the AC8A composite with aluminum borate whiskers. The AC8A matrix composite had also good strength beyond 400 MPa at room temperature and, furthermore, it maintained high strength up to elevated temperature. At 300°C the strength was about 250 MPa. This strength is similar value obtained in the composite reinforced with silicon carbide whisker.

Thus, aluminum borate whisker has almost comparable ability in reinforcing aluminum alloys as silicon carbide whisker and as silicon nitride whisker, which have been believed to be two of the best whiskers for aluminum matrix composites. In addition to such good characteristics, aluminum borate

whisker is known as one of the cheap whiskers as potassium titanate whisker, which enable us to use them to wide applications. Therefore, this whisker will be one of the best whiskers for aluminum matrix composites used in industries.

FIGURE 1. Comparison of tensile strength, Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient of 6061 matrix composites with various whiskers. Each composite contains 20 vol% reinforcing element.
 ALBO: aluminum borate whisker SC : silicon carbide whisker
 SN : silicon nitride whisker KTO : potassium titanate whisker
 ALO : alumina-silica short fiber

TABLE 2. Mechanical and thermal properties of AC8A alloy and AC8A matrix composite with 20 vol% aluminum borate whisker(FRM).

	0.2% proof stress(MPa)	Tensile strength(MPa)	Elongation (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Thermal expansion coefficient(°C)
AC8A	203	265	0.7	71	22.8 × 10 ⁻⁶
FRM	369	427	0.5	107	14.7 × 10 ⁻⁶

FIGURE 2. Temperature dependence of tensile strength of AC8A and AC8A matrix composite reinforced with aluminum borate whiskers

3.2 Microstructures Dispersion microstructures of aluminum borate whisker were almost the same both in the 6061 matrix composite and in the AC8A one. Figure 3 shows microstructures of AC8A alloy and the AC8A matrix composite with aluminum borate whiskers. Large precipitates are observed in the AC8A alloy and those are believed to be silicon and intermetallic compounds of the alloying elements. On the contrary, the composite showed very fine structure. Those precipitates dispersed finely among whiskers, which is one of the typical phenomena observed in whisker reinforced aluminum alloys. In a macroscopic observation, no severe reaction of the whiskers with aluminum matrices was recognized.

Figure 4 shows the TEM micrograph of the whisker in the 6061 matrix. Some fine precipitates are observed on the whisker surface. X-ray diffraction analysis of the extracted whiskers indicated the formation of spinel ($MgAl_2O_4$ or $\gamma-Al_2O_3$) and, therefore, those seem to be the spinel precipitates. Figure 5 shows the spinel precipitates on the whisker surface with diffraction pattern and EDX analysis. The whisker surface have fine steps and the spinel precipitates are formed on those tops.

FIGURE 3. Microstructures of AC8A alloy and AC8A matrix composite with aluminum borate whiskers (OM)

FIGURE 4. Aluminum borate whisker in 6061 matrix(TEM).

FIGURE 5. TEM micrograph of the spinel formation on the aluminum borate whisker with EDX analysis of one of the precipitates and with the diffraction pattern from the whisker and precipitates. The incident beam is parallel to the [100] direction of the whisker and the whisker lies on the sheet.

Slight amount of magnesium was recognized in the EDX profile. Because the whisker has aluminum as one of the main elements which might influence on the EDX analysis of the precipitate, the ratio of magnesium to aluminum in the precipitate was not consistent with that of the $MgAl_2O_4$ compound. The diffraction patterns from the several precipitates were all in one diffraction spot which indicated by the arrow and the corresponding lattice image in the precipitates showed the same orientation relationship. Those observations indicate that the spinel precipitates have a certain orientation relationship with the whisker.

Figure 6 shows HREM of the interface between the whisker and the precipitate. Two lattice fringes crossing each other and having the same spacing are observed in the precipitate. These were determined to be the {111} planes of the spinel. The precipitates are the parallelogram surrounded by the {111} planes. Although this spinel precipitate does not have a perfect lattice, it shows a good epitaxial relationship with the whisker which is expressed as following.

The aluminum borate whisker has a orthorhombic structure and it has the c-axis as the growing whisker axis. It has a rectangular cross section surrounded by $\{010\}$ and $\{100\}$ planes with the flat corners of $\{110\}$ planes(3). Therefore, there may be the other types of orientation relationships on the $\{110\}$ and $\{100\}$ planes. Anyway, the spinel precipitates formed on the aluminum borate whisker have quite good epitaxial relationship with the whisker. This fact may indicate the tight bonding at the interface.

FIGURE 6. HREM of the spinel/whisker interface (the same view as Figure 4). The extra (111) planes which do not connect with the (001) planes are indicated by the arrows "A".

3.3 Reaction of aluminum borate whisker with aluminum alloys As shown in the foregoing sections, the aluminum borate whisker does not react severely with aluminum alloys under squeeze casting condition. Only a slight reaction takes place at the surface layer of an whisker to form fine spinel precipitates adhering tightly to the whisker. There is no thermodynamic data available for explaining the reaction between aluminum borate/aluminum alloys.

This reaction process can be expressed as following equation.

$\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ has the spinel crystal structure and it is easy to convert into MgAl_2O_4 if the matrix contains magnesium as one of the alloying elements(4). The solubility of the other element formed by the reaction, boron, is very small even in a aluminum liquid (less than 0.5 at% at 785°C) and is negligibly small in a solid aluminum matrix(5). Therefore, boron may precipitate in a matrix or be released from the composite. Microstructural observation even by X-ray diffraction did not detect any precipitation of boron crystal. One possible evidence is observed in Figures 4 and 5. There is an amorphous-like structure at the bottom of the hollows formed on the whisker surface.

It's not possible to identify it because it form narrow structure which is far below the spatial resolution of the EDX. Figure 7 shows the same structure in the aluminum borate whisker/6061 matrix interface. The amorphous-like layer is quite thin, about 1 nm. This layer seems to be formed as on kind of the reaction front structures. Such a thin amorphous-like layer has been also observed at the interface between the potassium titanate whisker/aluminum system(4) but not at the interfaces of the silicon nitride whisker/aluminum and of the silicon carbide whisker/aluminum. One of the differences between those two categories is whether the reaction system contains a low solubility element in a matrix or not. In the potassium titanate whisker/aluminum reaction system, potassium is released after the reaction and its solubility is also negligible in aluminum matrices.

The reaction process between the aluminum borate whisker and aluminum alloys forming steps with spinel precipitates on them is illustrated as Figure 8. At the beginning of the reaction, the whisker decomposes into alumina releasing oxygen and boron atoms. The oxygen easily combines with aluminum to form γ -alumina. If the matrix contains magnesium as the alloying elements, magnesium is taken into γ -alumina to form spinel(MgAl_2O_4). The areas on the whisker surface where the γ -alumina or spinel precipitates

FIGURE 7. HREM of aluminum borate whisker/6061 matrix interface. Electron beam incidents along the c-axis of the whisker and the interface is edge-on. Two or three lattice fringes, (111) planes of the aluminum matrix, disappear. The thickness of the amorphous-like layer varied position to position.

FIGURE 8. Reaction process of aluminum borate whisker with aluminum matrices.

adhere tightly and cover are protected from the further reaction. The concave portions are eroded as proceeding the reaction. Finally, the whisker has steps on the surface with fine spinel precipitates.

4.CONCLUSIONS

The present work has presented the potentials of the aluminum borate whisker in reinforcing aluminum matrix composites and has identified the interfacial structure. Results obtained can be summarized as following.

- 1.The aluminum matrix composites reinforced with the aluminum borate whisker have high strength up to elevated temperatures. Young's modulus is also high and thermal expansion coefficient is small. Those properties are comparable to those of the conventional high quality whisker reinforced composites.
- 2.The reaction between aluminum borate whisker and aluminum alloy was not severe. Fine precipitates were formed on steps formed on the whisker. These were determined to be spinel ($MgAl_2O_4$ or $\gamma-Al_2O_3$).
- 3.A thin amorphous-like layer was formed at the direct interface between the whisker and the matrix.

The interface structure in a composite must have a great influence on properties of the composite. However, there has been no idea established for the ideal interface in metal matrix composites. Tight interface will be desirable for ductile matrix composites. The present composite system, however, has the special interface structures consisting of the steps with the tightly adhering spinel precipitates on them and the amorphous-like thin interlayer at the whisker/matrix direct interface. At this moment it is possible to conclude that such fine precipitates in a few nm scale on an whisker does not make serious damage on the quality of aluminum matrix composites. The aluminum borate whisker is proved to be one of the quite useful whiskers not only because of its ability to reinforce aluminum alloys but of its low cost. The latter factor sometimes becomes critical when the composites are to be used in wide industries.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Mr.H.Hta(Shikoku Chemicals, Co.) for supplying aluminum borate whisker and for his helpful discussions.

REFERENCES

1. T. Donomoto, N. Miura, K. Funatani and N. Miyake, SAE Paper Series, No.830252 (1984).
2. K. Suganuma, T. Fujita, N. Suzuki and K. Niihara, J.Mater.Sci.Letters, 9 633 (1990).
3. K. Suganuma, G. Sasaki, T. Fujita and N. Suzuki, J.Japan.Inst.Light Metals, (1991), in press.
4. K. Suganuma, T. Fujita, K. Niihara and N. Suzuki, J.Japan Inst.Metals, 54 (12), 1422 (1990).
5. M. Hansen and K. Anderko, Constitution of Binary Alloys, 2nd, McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1986, pp.70.